

Automated Model Interpretation, Pattern Analysis and Insights in Explainable AI

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Abstract

Deep learning has revolutionized artificial intelligence by enabling highly accurate models across diverse domains such as computer vision and autonomous driving. However, the inherent complexity of deep neural networks often results in *black-box* models, whose decision-making processes lack transparency and interpretability. Explainable Artificial Intelligence addresses this challenge by developing techniques that make model predictions more understandable to humans. Among these, Class Activation Mapping (CAM) and its variants: Grad-CAM, Grad-CAM++ and Score-CAM, have become pivotal in providing visual explanations for convolutional neural networks. This paper presents a systematic comparison of several prominent CAM-based explanation methods applied to the AlexNet architecture on a standardized Dogs vs. Cats image dataset. We evaluate these methods using quantitative metrics including Intersection over Union, Dice coefficient and Deletion and Insertion tests, aiming to reveal their respective strengths, limitations and practical utility. These findings offer valuable insights to guide practitioners in selecting appropriate explanation techniques. Specifically, we show that combining CAM-based techniques enables a deeper understanding of pixel importance by identifying critical regions composed of both object and background pixels and by guiding data preprocessing promotes more stable training and improves the model's focus. Furthermore, we demonstrate the potential for constructing robust feature attribution strategies grounded in layer-wise analysis and assess the reliability of various XAI algorithms by evaluating their behavior across multiple threshold levels.

1 Introduction

Deep learning, a subset of machine learning, has become a cornerstone of artificial intelligence (AI). Inspired by the human brain's neural networks, deep learning has found applications across a wide range of fields, including computer vision, natural language processing, healthcare and autonomous driving. However, as AI systems increase in complexity and capability, a critical challenge has surfaced: the lack of transparency and interpretability in the decision-making processes of deep neural

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networks [1], [2]. Often referred to as "black-box" models, these systems can be remarkably accurate while remaining opaque, making it difficult to understand why a particular prediction was made.

To address this challenge, Explainable AI (XAI) [10] [11] has become a key area in machine learning, aiming to make model decisions more transparent and interpretable. In the context of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), visual explanation methods such as Class Activation Mapping (CAM) [12], along with its variants like Grad-CAM [13], Grad-CAM++ [14] or Score-CAM [15], have emerged as foundational tools in decisions understanding and interpreting.

These algorithms provide visual explanations by highlighting input regions that most influence a model's decision. Grad-CAM, for instance, uses class-specific gradients from the final convolutional layer to generate coarse heatmaps that reveal model reasoning. Later variants improved spatial resolution, class sensitivity, and robustness across architectures. However, no single method is universally optimal, prompting comparative evaluations of CAM-based techniques [4, 5]. Each variant involves trade-offs in fidelity, localization accuracy, computational cost, and resilience to input changes. Their effectiveness also depends on the model architecture, dataset type, and interpretability metrics. Choosing the best CAM variant for a specific task remains challenging, motivating further comparative analysis under controlled conditions.

Recent advances in Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) aim to improve trust, accountability, and transparency in black-box models. Modern XAI methods are structured around the types of questions users might ask, such as: "Why was this decision made?", "Why not another outcome?" or "How can I achieve a different prediction?" [3][10]. Studies demonstrate that regions highlighted by activation maps can effectively be used to suppress background noise or emphasize salient regions, thereby improving model focus and training stability [7].

A diverse set of XAI techniques contributes to model interpretability at different levels. Instance-level methods such as LIME and SHAP provide localized insights by identifying key input features that drive predictions [2][22], while counterfactual approaches like CEM and DiCE explain how minimal input changes could alter model output [23]. Global techniques, including feature importance scores and surrogate models, offer a broader understanding of the model's decision logic. To more rigorously assess the quality of saliency-based explanations, insertion and deletion tests have been introduced [8], which measure the impact of progressively removing or enhancing salient regions on model confidence. Additionally, layer-wise attribution strategies—such as aggregating Class Activation Maps (CAMs) from multiple convolutional layers using weighted averages, max-pooling, or PCA fusion—have been shown to produce richer and more reliable heatmaps [7].

The purpose of this article is to make a systematic comparison of several prominent CAM-based explanation algorithms with a focus on understanding their strengths, limitations and practical utility. By applying each method to a standardized image classification task, we seek to evaluate them using concrete and, in some cases, already well-established metrics, that we find more suitable than

visual coherence and human intuition, such as Intersection over Union (IoU) [25], Dice [26], Deletion and Insertion Tests [24].

The main innovation of our work lies in combining systematic benchmarking of CAM-based methods, layer-wise visual analysis, and the practical use of XAI techniques to guide data preprocessing and improve model training- all evaluated using standardized quantitative metrics. While CAM, Grad-CAM, Grad-CAM++, and Score-CAM are established methods, our systematic and architecture-specific evaluation on AlexNet offers new practical insights. Furthermore, demonstrating that CAM-based explainability tools can support preprocessing decisions and enhance training stability represents a practical and relatively underexplored application. We show that visualizations can help optimize both input selection and model behavior, which we believe is a meaningful contribution to the field.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Class Activation Mapping Techniques

Gradient-weighted Class Activation Mapping (Grad-CAM) [13] generates visual explanations for CNN-based models by computing the gradients of the target class score with respect to convolutional feature maps. These are globally averaged to obtain weights, which produce a heatmap highlighting important input regions. Grad-CAM++ [14], an extension of Grad-CAM, improves object feature localization by generating more precise, interpretable heatmaps. It uses a weighted sum of positive partial derivatives from the last convolutional layer with respect to the target class score.

A gradient-free approach is exemplified by Score-CAM[15], which determines the importance of each activation map by forward-passing masked inputs through the model and measuring the change in the target class score. This method often produces even more reliable and visually appealing explanations, as it is less susceptible to issues such as gradient saturation.

2.2 Attribution Methods: Neuron, Layer and Feature Attribution

Neuron attribution[18] methods provide the most in-depth perspective by assigning relevance to individual neurons. They aim to identify which neurons are most active for a given output and how their activation patterns impact the prediction. Although this level of detail provides deep insight into the model’s inner workings, it often presents challenges in terms of intuitive human interpretation.

Focusing on the contributions of intermediate layers, Layer attribution[18] aims to explain how different layers of the network influence the model’s output. Instead of analyzing input features directly, layer attribution reveals how information is transformed and propagated through the network’s hierarchical structure.

CAM techniques naturally lend themselves to layer attribution. Grad-CAM output offers a novel semi-temporal insight into how representations evolve through-

out the convolutional layers of the network. Although CNNs are not inherently sequential models in time, viewing activations as a sequence reveals patterns of increasing abstraction and spatial refinement as one moves deeper into the network. This methodology allows an intuitive understanding of how progressively deeper layers refine and abstract the input information.

Feature attribution [17] methods aim to assign importance scores to individual input features (such as pixels in an image) relative to a model’s prediction. These techniques attempt to identify which parts of the input were most influential for this decision. Prominent examples include gradient-based saliency maps, integrated gradients or LIME [6].

Complementing the layer attribution analysis, several feature attribution strategies can be adopted to gain a more detailed understanding of how individual input features contribute to a model’s prediction.

Simple averaging the Grad-CAM outputs across all considered layers to produce a composite heatmap, summarizing feature importance throughout the network. In contrast, a weighted average assigns linearly increasing weights to deeper layers, reflecting the intuition that deeper features tend to be more abstract and semantically meaningful. The weights increase linearly with the layer depth. Max Pooling Across Layers selects the pixel-wise maximum from all individual Grad-CAM maps, highlighting the most salient signals regardless of the originating layer.

Principal Component Fusion is a widely used, model-agnostic, and user-friendly interpretability technique that produces easily understandable outputs without requiring additional training or retraining. This approach stacks all Grad-CAM maps into a 3D tensor with shape $[L, H, W]$, where L denotes the number of layers and H, W are the spatial dimensions of the input. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is then applied to extract the dominant attribution patterns across layers, effectively summarizing the most informative features.

2.3 Model Description

The AlexNet model [16] marked a significant breakthrough in deep learning, especially in computer vision. Its relatively shallow depth and simple architecture make it well-suited for early explorations of XAI methods, enabling visualization techniques like Grad-CAM to clearly reveal the progressive feature transformations across convolutional layers. This model was chosen for its simplicity and widespread recognition in the literature. In our study, AlexNet serves solely as a tool for conducting a comparative analysis of different XAI approaches.

To simplify the task and enable focused analysis, a binary classification problem was used: distinguishing cats from dogs. This approach employs the well-known Dogs vs. Cats dataset[9], which includes approximately 25,000 labeled training images and 12,154 labeled test images, with a balanced 50/50 class split. The goal was not to achieve state-of-the-art accuracy, but to obtain a sufficiently trained model for generating and analyzing attribution maps.

Table 1: Overview of preprocessing strategies used in the experiments.

Heading level	Example Description
Original dataset	Standard training on the original dataset, used as a reference baseline.
Blurred background	Background regions (outside the animal) are blurred with a Gaussian filter, encouraging the model to focus on the object of interest.
Blacked-out background	Background pixels are replaced with black, isolating the subject more clearly.
Cropped background	Images are cropped tightly around the foreground object (the cat or dog) to eliminate contextual background.
CAM-based blurring	Gaussian blur with a 21×21 kernel is applied to regions where the CAM heatmap value is below a threshold (0.4, 0.3, or 0.2).
CAM deletion	Salient pixels are progressively removed based on their importance and the model’s confidence. The resulting confidence degradation is summarized by the Area Under the Curve (AUC). A low AUC (below 0.50) suggests those regions can be discarded.
Augmented dataset	CAM-guided crops retain only the most discriminative regions of each image. Images tend to appear bluer due to the reduced presence of warm-toned background areas.

3 Explainable AI Approach

XAI methods were employed to enhance model interpretability and guide data preprocessing decisions. Specifically, the presented CAM techniques were used to generate saliency heatmaps that highlight the most relevant regions in the input images. These techniques build upon prior work that combines CAM-based analysis with data augmentation strategies presented in Table 1.

The flexibility of augmentation and preprocessing methods offers a wide range of training strategies to explore model behavior and improve result quality, while gaining a deeper understanding of the data’s specific characteristics.

Each training condition was quantitatively evaluated using a dedicated evaluation pipeline. In addition to classification metrics, a separate benchmarking procedure was applied to measure model efficiency under each training condition. To this end, each trained model was executed multiple times over the same test dataset to record average inference time and standard deviation.

Figure 1: Layer attribution results

4 Results and Interpretation

The performance of each described technique is evaluated using different metrics and from various perspectives. Implementations of the following methods are available in a public GitHub repository [19].

4.1 Heatmap Visualization

Figure 1 presents heatmap visualizations for each layer of the pretrained AlexNet model [7], based on a randomly selected sample from the test dataset. Each of the five layers shown includes heatmaps generated using the CAM-based methods: Grad-CAM, Grad-CAM++ and Score-CAM, presented in this order.

The intensity of the colors in the heatmap reflects how much each pixel contributes to the model’s decision. Red and yellow areas indicate high importance, red typically representing attribution values around 0.77 and about 0.63 for yellow. Meanwhile, green and light blue areas signify lower importance, usually values of about 0.50. In contrast, dark blue and purple regions are typically disregarded by the model, often corresponding to background or irrelevant areas, with attribution values around 0.16. These color-coded activations are obtained by applying a ReLU operation to the weighted sum of the final convolutional layer’s feature maps, highlighting only the positive contributions to the predicted class. Based on the frames in Figure 1, we observe how each pixel’s importance varies across layers, revealing the regions most relevant to the model’s prediction. Each CAM method highlights different areas throughout the network, particularly around the object of interest—the dog. However, at the final convolutional layer, all three methods converge on the dog’s face, indicating it as the key region driving the classification.

For a deeper understanding and more robust explainability, it is important to

Figure 2: Feature attribution maps.

observe how the heatmaps across different layers converge to highlight consistent regions of interest in the image. This convergence supports meaningful conclusions about which parts of the input are most relevant to the model’s prediction. A visual representation of this convergence is provided in Figure 2.

Analyzing the generated heatmaps allows us to assess the fidelity of CAM-based explanations and the alignment between saliency regions and the actual semantic object in the image. It becomes evident that the region containing the dog is crucial for the model’s decision, especially the defining features of the animal. Additionally, the visualizations reveal how the model handles background areas and transitional pixels, indicating a relevant influence from those regions.

4.2 Overlap with Segmentation Ground Truth

To support a stronger and more precise conclusion regarding the importance of the region of interest compared to the background, an evaluation was conducted using a binary segmentation mask. This ground truth mask assigns a value of 1 to pixels belonging to the animal and 0 to those corresponding to the background.

To objectively assess the quality of the generated attribution maps, we adopt several established evaluation metrics. By applying a threshold of 0.5 to the CAM maps, binary importance masks were produced, used to compute overlap metrics. These values are computed using two standard metrics, as shown in Equation 1: the IoU, which measures the ratio between the overlap and the total area covered by both masks, and the Dice Coefficient, which represents the harmonic mean of precision and recall at the pixel level.

Table 2: Evaluation metrics

CAM Algorithm	Feature Attribution	IoU	Dice
GradCAM	PCA-fusion	0.2111	0.3487
	Average	0.2150	0.3540
	Max-pooling	0.2199	0.3606
	Weighted-average	0.2150	0.3540
GradCAM++	PCA-fusion	0.2912	0.4511
	Average	0.2757	0.4322
	Max-pooling	0.2295	0.3734
	Weighted-average	0.2757	0.4322
ScoreCAM	PCA-fusion	0.2909	0.4507
	Average	0.2546	0.4059
	Max-pooling	0.2135	0.3519
	Weighted-average	0.2546	0.4059

$$IoU(A, B) = \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|}, \quad Dice(A, B) = \frac{2|A \cap B|}{|A| + |B|} \quad (1)$$

The evaluation results presented in Table 2 show that all scores remain below 0.45, indicating that less than half of the object of interest is consistently identified as relevant by the model. This suggests limited overlap between the attribution maps and the ground-truth segmentation.

The results also support that advanced CAM variants, such as Score-CAM, especially when combined with richer feature aggregation methods like PCA fusion, improve the fidelity of attribution. These combinations produce heatmaps that better align with the true object mask, enhancing interpretability.

4.3 Insertion/Deletion Tests

To evaluate whether the regions highlighted by an attribution method are truly informative, we analyzed how the model performs when only parts of the image are used for prediction. Figure 3 presents a graph showing the CAM scores obtained by progressively revealing the most important regions, helping estimate the number of pixels required for the model to make an accurate prediction.

The Insertion test [8] evaluates how quickly the model’s confidence increases as important features are progressively introduced into a blank or blurred baseline. A higher area under the curve (AUC) indicates more faithful attribution, as key features contribute significantly to the prediction when reintroduced. The Deletion test [8] measures how quickly the model’s confidence in the predicted class decreases as the most important features, as identified by the attribution map, are progressively removed from the input. A lower AUC reflects greater attribution quality, suggesting that the identified regions play a critical role in the model’s decision-making process.

Figure 3: Insertion and Deletion curves.

The Deletion metric showed that removing just 5%–10% of the most important pixels (according to the heatmaps) caused a large drop in prediction confidence. The Insertion metric, rose quickly as the first 10% of pixels were added, indicating that these pixels carry most of the class-relevant information. Good attribution map will identify both features that raise the model’s confidence when inserted, as well as features that cause the confidence to drop when removed.

4.4 CAM-Guided Preprocessing

Based on the methodology from Table 1, another way to utilize CAM maps is by combining CAM techniques with standard preprocessing steps during training. Table 3 presents the evaluation metrics, including Accuracy, F1 score, Precision and Recall. The results were computed on the testing dataset after training the model with consistent parameters but under different conditions, to evaluate the impact of modifying or removing pixels considered unimportant.

Removing irrelevant regions through CAM-based deletion and background alterations of blacking or blurring the background often provided slight performance

Table 3: Performance metrics under each data preprocessing strategy.

Condition	Accuracy	F1Score	Precision	Recall
Full original dataset	0.96955	0.97012	0.97091	0.96934
Cropped background	0.96502	0.96638	0.96341	0.96931
Blurred background	0.96857	0.96918	0.96918	0.96918
Blacked-out background	0.96083	0.96191	0.95412	0.96982
CAM Augmented images	0.96207	0.96331	0.95038	0.97660
CAM deletion	0.96651	0.96693	0.97381	0.96014
GradCAM (threshold 0.4)	0.97031	0.97089	0.97320	0.96860
GradCAM (threshold 0.3)	0.96842	0.96944	0.97015	0.96874
GradCAM (threshold 0.2)	0.96715	0.96872	0.96930	0.96814
GradCAM++ (threshold 0.4)	0.96911	0.96970	0.97104	0.96837
GradCAM++ (threshold 0.3)	0.96784	0.96890	0.96945	0.96835
GradCAM++ (threshold 0.2)	0.96670	0.96822	0.96741	0.96904
ScoreCAM (threshold 0.4)	0.97085	0.97133	0.97380	0.96912
ScoreCAM (threshold 0.3)	0.96945	0.97001	0.97151	0.96853
ScoreCAM (threshold 0.2)	0.96770	0.96820	0.96972	0.96669

gains for pretrained models, while cropping reduced context and tended to lower recall. Targeted blurring using CAM heatmaps showed threshold-dependent effects. For example, using Grad-CAM with a 0.4 threshold yielded a higher F1-score and accuracy than the full-dataset baseline, indicating that focusing on the most important 40% of pixels improved learning.

In this study, we start empirically with a threshold of 0.2 (only the top 20% most important pixels were retained) and progressively increased it by 0.1. This process continued as long as the classification accuracy remained lower than or equal to the baseline accuracy obtained on the original dataset.

Applying a CAM-based preprocessing methodology before inference affects processing time. Benchmarked on an AMD Ryzen 5 7600X CPU, Score-CAM introduced an average delay of 7.8 milliseconds, compared to 5.9 milliseconds for Grad-CAM and 6.1 milliseconds for Grad-CAM++. These delays are negligible when using a more powerful GPU.

5 Conclusions

Our experiments highlight the potential of CAM-based explanations to meaningfully guide data preprocessing in ways that improve model interpretability and performance. By leveraging relevance maps to focus the model on salient image regions, we observed consistent improvements in classification accuracy, particularly when using Grad-CAM++ and Score-CAM with medium thresholds (e.g., 0.2–0.4). These settings provided an optimal balance between model focus and contextual information retention. While background blurring or deletion showed minor yet positive effects, aggressive cropping often led to performance degra-

dation, notably in recall. This indicates that seemingly irrelevant background elements can still provide useful context for the model’s decisions.

Among the CAM variants, Score-CAM achieved the best spatial alignment with ground truth segmentation masks, as indicated by the highest IoU and Dice scores. However, this came at a substantial computational cost, significantly increasing inference time. In contrast, Grad-CAM++ provided a more favorable trade-off, offering notable performance gains with much lower latency.

Importantly, simpler preprocessing approaches such as CAM-based deletion or targeted blurring incurred minimal computational overhead while still enhancing interpretability. Interestingly, inference time analysis revealed that to the baseline AlexNet performed fastest, due to its lack of learned activations—emphasizing the computational load imposed by trained filters. Finally, perturbation-based evaluation metrics such as Insertion and Deletion proved more faithful in assessing explanation quality than segmentation-overlap metrics (IoU, Dice), aligning with prior findings [20][21]. Notably, deletion experiments showed that removing as little as 5% of the most salient pixels (according to heatmap scores) caused a sharp drop in model confidence, confirming the model’s strong dependence on a small set of critical features.

Together, these findings offer actionable insights for leveraging explanation techniques not only for model transparency, but also as tools for performance optimization and input refinement.

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